

“A Pious Fraud”: 20 year update

My “Pious Fraud” essay was presented at a conference in 1985, and published in the book *Studies on Indian Medical History* (1987, reprinted in 2001).

The article proposed that the source of the Sanskrit passage on cowpox vaccination was probably an document written by someone between 1802 and 1820, in order to promote vaccination. Trustworthy evidence was cited (2001, p. 134) showing that F. W. Ellis was known at the time to have done exactly this. However, his actual documents were believed to have been lost, burned by his cook after his death.

Prof. Thomas Trautmann has subsequently discovered an actual vaccination tract that Ellis composed in Tamil with an English translation. The tract is published in an appendix to Trautmann’s *Languages and nations: the Dravidian proof in colonial Madras* (2006), as Appendix A: “The Legend of the Cow-Pox” by F. W. Ellis, Esq. This can be read online (mostly) at [Google Books](#).

Trautmann’s discovery is a pleasing confirmation of the main argument of my “Pious Fraud” essay. Several passages of the Ellis tract come very close to the Sanskrit “*Saktéya Grantham*” text that appeared in the *Madras Courier* in 1820. Ellis’s piece is cast as a discussion between Śakti and Dhanvantari, and Kalvi Virumbon, who sent the *Saktéya Grantham* passage to the *Madras Courier*, said that his passage was in a book by Dhanvantari that was something to do with Śakti, which is what *Saktéya Grantham* (*śakteyagrantham*) means.

But Trautmann says (*Languages and Nations*, p. 231):

Dominik Wujastyk published a piece (1988 [*sic*]) based on newspaper reports about Ellis’s text, though he had not seen the English text published here and thought the original was in Sanskrit.

This is partly true, although I based my argument on much more evidence than just that of Ellis. But Trautmann is mistaken on the point about the Sanskrit. It is not that I thought the original was in Sanskrit, but that the *Madras Courier* text *is* in Sanskrit, albeit somewhat garbled.

Ellis’s tract, discovered and published by Trautmann, is another brick in the wall of the “Pious Fraud” argument. It makes it even more likely that Ellis was the source of the Sanskrit passage published in the *Madras Courier*, and suggests that “Kalvi Virumbon” may have been a pseudonym for Ellis himself.

However, it would be even more satisfying if the actual Sanskrit verse from the *Madras Courier* could be discovered verbatim, in Sanskrit or in an exact translation in original English, Tamil or other language.

Dominik Wujastyk,
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